

IgG4-Related Hypertrophic Pachymeningitis: A Great Clinical Imitator

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ABSTRACT

We present a diagnostically challenging case of a 45-year-old woman with a long-standing clinical course characterized by episodic dysphonia, epistaxis, seizures, and cranial neuropathies. Extensive evaluations initially led to a suspected diagnosis of non-Hodgkin lymphoma. However, elevated serum IgG4 levels and histopathological reevaluation confirmed IgG4-related hypertrophic pachymeningitis. The patient responded well to methotrexate and prednisone. This case underscores the importance of considering IgG4-RD in unexplained meningeal syndromes and highlights the need for timely recognition to avoid invasive interventions.

KEYWORDS: IgG4-related disease, hypertrophic pachymeningitis, autoimmune meningeal disease, corticosteroids, methotrexate

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INTRODUCTION

Immunoglobulin G4-related disease (IgG4-RD) is a systemic fibroinflammatory disorder characterized by tumefactive lesions, storiform fibrosis, and dense lymphoplasmacytic infiltrates rich in IgG4-positive plasma cells. Initially described in the context of autoimmune pancreatitis, its spectrum now includes over a dozen organ systems, such as the pancreas, salivary glands, retroperitoneum, and the central nervous system (CNS)¹

Hypertrophic pachymeningitis (HP) is one of the rare neurological manifestations of IgG4-RD, accounting for a subset of cases previously considered idiopathic. HP refers to localized or diffuse thickening of the dura mater, which can cause cranial neuropathies, seizures, and other focal deficits due to mass effect or nerve compression². The estimated prevalence of CNS involvement in IgG4-RD ranges from 1% to 8%, with pachymeningitis being the most common presentation³.

Diagnosis requires high clinical suspicion, supported by imaging, serum IgG4 quantification, and histopathologic

confirmation. Radiologically, HP typically presents as T1 isointense and T2 hypointense dural thickening with homogeneous gadolinium enhancement on MRI⁴. Early recognition is crucial, as immunosuppressive therapy can reverse symptoms and prevent long-term disability⁵

CASE REPORT

A 45-year-old female nurse began symptoms in 2012 with maxillary pain and submandibular adenopathy, unresponsive to dental extraction. Over the next years, she experienced episodic dysphonia, hypothermia, and nocturnal epistaxis. In 2014, seizures and holocranial headache appeared. Brain MRI showed frontal lobe abscess-like lesions and edema. Surgical drainage and biopsy suggested non-Hodgkin lymphoma, yet no pathogen was identified. After acyclovir treatment and a ventriculoperitoneal shunt in 2019, she developed right visual impairment. In 2022, IgG4 serum levels reached 1910 mg/dl. Histopathology review confirmed IgG4-RD. Methotrexate and prednisone led to full remission within a year.

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Figure 1: Brain MRI showing right frontal meningeal thickening and edema

Figure 2: Immunohistochemistry showing strong IgG4-positive plasma cell infiltration.

DISCUSSION

IgG4-related HP remains underrecognized due to its protean manifestations and overlap with infections, malignancies, and other autoimmune disorders such as granulomatosis with polyangiitis or neurosarcoidosis^{3 6}. In our patient, the long delay in diagnosis reflects this diagnostic ambiguity, despite recurrent neurological events and imaging suggestive of dural disease. Histological confirmation is essential for definitive diagnosis. The 2019 ACR/EULAR classification criteria require a combination of histopathological findings (storiform fibrosis, obliterative phlebitis, and IgG4+ plasma cells), serologic elevation of IgG4, and exclusion of other etiologies¹. However, some patients may have normal serum IgG4, underscoring the value of biopsy and immunohistochemistry⁶. Therapeutically, glucocorticoids remain first-line treatment, inducing remission in up to 90% of patients. In steroid-resistant or relapsing cases, steroid-sparing agents like azathioprine, mycophenolate, or methotrexate can be added. Rituximab has emerged as an effective alternative, especially in multi-organ involvement or recurrent disease⁷.

MRI findings such as dural thickening and gadolinium enhancement help localize disease but are not pathognomonic. Differential diagnoses include infectious meningitis (e.g., TB, syphilis), neoplastic infiltration (lymphoma, metastasis), and granulomatous diseases. Therefore, biopsy remains indispensable when imaging and clinical data are inconclusive^{2 4}.

CONCLUSION

This case exemplifies the complexity of diagnosing IgG4-related hypertrophic pachymeningitis and underscores the importance of considering IgG4-RD in patients with chronic, unexplained neurological symptoms and meningeal imaging findings. Timely diagnosis and appropriate immunosuppressive therapy can reverse symptoms and prevent long-term disability. Multidisciplinary collaboration is essential to reduce diagnostic delays and optimize outcome.

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